

A NEW ANGLE DEFINITION: CIRCLE SECTOR

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When looking at the relevant references, it is easy to see the misconceptions that the classical definition of angle causes in students. As can be seen from these misconceptions, it is time for a new definition of the angle, including both static and dynamic definitions, to be included in textbooks for a more accurate understanding of the angle. In order to eliminate these misconceptions and to provide a more accurate definition of angles, we give a new definition of angle below.

Definition: Consider two straight line segments, one fixed and one movable, placed at the center of a circle. The sector of the circle obtained by rotating the movable line counterclockwise is called an angle.

Question: What does it mean to measure an angle?

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Answer: Finding the number of degrees of the arc in the circle that forms the angle is called measuring the angle.

Question: According to this new definition, what are the teaching stages of the angle?

Answer: According to this new definition, the first step is to draw a circle in the plane. Before placing any line segment inside this circle, it is explained to the students that the arc of the circle consists of a 360-degree arc and this is called a full angle. Then place a fixed straight line segment at the center of the circle. Subsequently, the moving straight line segment is placed within the same circle and then rotated counterclockwise, defining the resulting sector as an angle.

The effectiveness and validity of this definition will be revealed by testing the teaching models that will be based on this definition by mathematics teachers and mathematics educators who are experts in their field.